

Temperature tolerance

Rice response to extreme temperatures in Saudi Arabia

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Winter and summer 1976 crops of 36 rices, including cultivars from Africa, Australia, India, IRRI, Japan, Korea, Saudi Arabia, and Taiwan, were observed for their reactions to extremely low and high temperatures (Table 1) at Al-Hassa Oasis, the main rice-growing area in Saudi Arabia.

Low spring temperatures affected the early growth of winter rice, particularly that of indicas, although most recovered eventually. Decreasing fall temperatures appeared not to harm the ripening summer crop. High temperatures during later growing stages of the winter crop damaged only the grain filling of traditional tropical rices and YR lines

from Australia, but not that of japonicas from Japan and Taiwan. Vegetative growth of the summer crop, especially of japonicas, was severely stunted by intense heat and strong sunlight during early growth. Heat stress was also reflected in the low fertility of japonica rices; indicas ripened normally (Table 2). Grain yields (expressed in panicle weight per plant) of the summer crop, except of the tropical rices, were considerably lower than those of the winter crop. The findings suggest that high yielding semidwarf indica and japonica rices can be grown successfully as winter crops in Al-Hassa. For the hot summer crop, the modern rices are apparently not as well adapted as the traditional rices. Marked differences in varietal responses, however, suggest that improved varieties better suited to local conditions could be selected.

Table 1. Average temperature during several growth stages of winter and summer crops, Al-Hassa, Saudi Arabia, 1976.

Growth stage	Temperature (°C)			
	Winter crops		Summer crops	
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.
Transplanting	11.5	31.4	17.8	46.8
Heading-ripening	16.5–16.4	42.8–46.3	15.9–14.7	45.0–43.2
Average (10 a.m.)	31.4	34.6	38.5	42.3

Table 2. Performance of winter (W) and summer (S) rice crops, Al-Hassa, Saudi Arabia, 1976.

Plant type	Fertility (%)		Panicle weight (g/plant)	
	W	S	W	S
	Indica			
Semidwarf	86.8	87.5	55.8	36.2
Tropical	30.4	87.3	26.8	46.8
YR Line	22.7	35.8	18.6	12.1
Mean	46.6	70.2	33.7	31.7
Japonica				
Japanese	80.8	10.4	44.3	3.0
Ponlai	90.9	37.7	61.5	10.1
Mean	85.9	24.1	52.9	6.6

Adverse soils

Varietal tolerance of rice to iron toxicity in Liberia

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Iron toxicity and associated nutrient disorders of rice occur widely in swamp valleys newly developed for rice in Liberia and in similar regions in other West African countries. Yield reductions of 10 to 90% have been recorded in the affected areas. Symptoms vary, depending on the variety and the type of imbalance. Bronzing of the leaves starting at the tips is characteristic, but orange or yellowing of leaves may occur; stunting may occur, with scanty root production and spikelet sterility.

In 3 years, 1,400 lines have been screened at the Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko, in an iron-toxic swamp (pH less than 5, organic matter 5%) that is irrigated by seepage water containing a high level of soluble iron. Most lines have been eliminated from further consideration. Gissi 27, a photoperiod-sensitive local variety, has been found to be consistently tolerant. At maximum tillering its leaves contain 560 ppm iron, compared with 1,650 and 1,720 ppm contained in leaves of the susceptible lines IR269-26-3-3-3 and IR589-54-2. Several lines derived from IR2031, IR2053, IR2070, IR2071, IR2153, and IR2688 have been observed to be tolerant. They involve iron-toxicity-tolerant lines (IR20, IR1416-131-5, and CR94-13) in their parentage. Tolerance appears to be heritable. Some lines from Sri Lanka (Dewarederri, BW191, BW196, BG35-2), Indonesia (B 1896-29-4-3-1, B 4596-Pn-132-3-5, B 459-Pn-132-8-1, B 462-CPn-1-3), and Malaysia (2526, Improved Mahsuri) are also tolerant. Screening and crossing of more germ plasm from those entries should help to develop improved iron-toxicity-tolerant varieties. Several dry-land varieties –